

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

A Case Report

**"FULL-HOUSE NEPHROPATHY WITHOUT LUPUS: A UNIQUE
PRESENTATION OF SEVERE PROTEINURIA IN AN ELDERLY
PATIENT"****¹Haider Sarfaraz*, ²Syed Aftab Ahmad, ¹Muhammad Abbas, ¹Malik Hasnat ul Hassan
Khan.**¹MTI-Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar Pakistan.²MTI-Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar Pakistan.**Abstract:**

We report a rare case of a 74-year-old male presenting with nephrotic-range proteinuria, impaired renal function, and mild tubular and interstitial changes. Initial investigations, including an ultrasound of the kidneys and an echocardiogram, were unremarkable. However, the patient's worsening renal function and significant proteinuria prompted a renal biopsy, which revealed full-house nephropathy, characterized by the presence of immune deposits including IgA, IgG, IgM, C3, and C1q. Despite these findings, there was no evidence of crescent formation, necrosis, or global glomerular sclerosis. Additionally, the patient had no clinical or serological evidence of systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), a condition typically associated with full-house nephropathy.

Full-house nephropathy is most commonly seen in lupus nephritis, where immune complexes deposit within the glomeruli, leading to significant kidney damage. The presence of this pattern in non-lupus cases, as seen in this patient, is not common. In this case, despite the severe proteinuria and clinical deterioration, the histopathological findings were relatively mild, with only diffuse endocapillary proliferative glomerulonephritis, mild tubular damage, and limited interstitial fibrosis.

This case highlights the unusual presentation of full-house nephropathy in the absence of lupus and emphasizes the importance of considering alternative diagnoses when faced with this histological pattern. It also raises questions about the pathophysiology of full-house nephropathy in non-lupus patients and suggests that clinical outcomes may vary significantly depending on the underlying etiology.

Keywords: Idiopathic, full house nephropathy, immunofluorescence, lupus nephritis, Proteinuria

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Please cite this article in press Haider Sarfaraz et al., "Full-House Nephropathy Without Lupus: A Unique Presentation Of Severe Proteinuria In An Elderly Patient" ..,Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (10).

INTRODUCTION:

Full-house immunofluorescence in a kidney biopsy means that all 5 major immunofluorescent stains on a renal biopsy (IgG, IgA, IgM, C3, and C1Q) are positive [1]. Full-house immunofluorescence is a typical finding in renal biopsies of patients with lupus nephritis (LN) [2]. Non-lupus full-house nephropathy is rare and is poorly understood [3]. Non-lupus full-house nephropathy is an umbrella term for such cases which do not satisfy the standard criteria of SLE. In literature conditions are reported to have full house immunostaining pattern on immunofluorescence including membranous nephropathy (MN), IgA nephropathy, membranoproliferative GN (MPGN), post-infectious GN (PIGN), C1Q nephropathy, and unclassified mesangial GN [1]. In elderly patients, the presence of diffuse proliferative glomerulonephritis with full-house deposits, without typical lupus features, is highly unusual [4].

The microanatomical structural changes of the kidney with older age include a decreased number of functional glomeruli from an increased prevalence of nephrosclerosis (arteriosclerosis, glomerulosclerosis, and tubular atrophy with interstitial fibrosis), and to some extent, compensatory hypertrophy of remaining nephrons [5], but in this case, these features were conspicuously absent.

Furthermore, the presence of eosinophilic infiltrates in the renal interstitium raises the possibility of drug-induced interstitial nephritis [6], which, in combination with full-house deposits, further complicates the diagnostic landscape.

Case Presentation:

A 74-year-old male presented with a one-week history of fever, generalized body swelling, shortness of breath, orthopnea, and vomiting. Upon admission, his blood pressure was elevated at 170/100 mmHg. Notably, the patient had no prior medical history of significance and no known comorbidities. The constellation of symptoms suggested a complex underlying condition, potentially involving the cardiovascular, renal, or systemic inflammatory systems.

On physical examination, the patient exhibited bilateral pedal edema and reduced air entry in both lungs, raising suspicion of fluid overload and potential pulmonary involvement. Hematuria was also observed, which pointed to possible underlying renal pathology. Despite these findings, an initial ultrasound of the kidneys, ureters, and bladder (KUB) showed no abnormalities, and an echocardiogram revealed a normal ejection fraction, ruling out systolic heart

failure. The normal echocardiogram was significant as it indicated that the patient's shortness of breath and orthopnea were unlikely due to systolic dysfunction, although diastolic heart failure remained a possibility. The overall clinical picture, characterized by generalized edema, respiratory symptoms, hematuria, and elevated blood pressure, suggested fluid overload or a systemic disease with multi-organ involvement. Given the patient's presentation, further investigation was essential to reach a definitive diagnosis. Laboratory findings were significant for severe proteinuria, hypoalbuminemia, and elevated serum creatinine and blood urea nitrogen (BUN), pointing to kidney involvement. In light of worsening renal function and the systemic symptoms, a renal biopsy was performed.

The renal biopsy revealed key pathological findings. Of the 25 glomeruli examined, a diffuse endocapillary proliferative pattern of glomerulonephritis was observed, consistent with an inflammatory process in the kidneys. Importantly, none of the glomeruli showed global sclerosis, which was a positive prognostic indicator. Additional findings included mild medial hypertrophy of the blood vessels, mild tubular damage, and mild tubulointerstitial nephritis, all suggestive of chronic but relatively mild kidney injury. Mild interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy were present, indicating ongoing chronic injury, although the degree of damage was limited.

Crucially, immunofluorescence staining revealed "full-house" deposits, including immunoglobulins IgA, IgG, and IgM, as well as complement components C3 and C1q. This "full-house" pattern is typically associated with lupus nephritis or other autoimmune glomerulonephritides. However, despite this finding, extensive serological and clinical workup for systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) was negative. The patient exhibited no clinical signs of lupus, and serological markers, including antinuclear antibody (ANA) and anti-double-stranded DNA (anti-dsDNA), were both negative, effectively ruling out SLE. Despite the absence of lupus serology and clinical manifestations, the renal biopsy showed the characteristic immunofluorescence pattern of lupus nephritis.

This case represents an unusual presentation of full-house nephropathy in the absence of SLE, a condition typically associated with this histopathological finding. The presence of significant proteinuria, mild histological changes, and negative SLE workup makes this case particularly rare and emphasizes the need to explore alternative diagnoses when encountering this unique immunofluorescence pattern.

TABLE 1: Basic lab investigations

Parameter	Value	Reference range
Total Leukocyte Count	7760/ul	4000-11000/ul
Hemoglobin	10.4g/dl	11.5-17.5 g/dl
Platelets	287000/ul	150000-450000/ul
MCV	84.7 fl	76-96 fl
HbsAg(By ICT)	Negative	Negative
Anti HCV (By ICT)	Negative	Negative
Anti HIV (By ICT)	Negative	Negative
Serum Creatinine	2.58 mg /dl	0.3-0.9 mg/dl
BUN	110.77 mg/dl	18-45 mg/dl
Serum Albumin	2.8 g/dl	3.5-5.5 g/dl
Serum Calcium	7.8 mg/dl	8.0-10 mg/dl
Total Bilirubin	0.2 mg/dl	0.1-1.0 mg/dl
ALT	30 U/L	10-50 U/L
ALP	101 U/L	>187 U/L
ESR	50 mm / 1 st hour	0-20 mm /1 st hour
CRP	<0.4 mg/dl	<1.0 mg/dl
D-Dimer	350ng/ml	Upto 200
Serum Ferritin	21ng/ml	13-150
Cholesterol	178 mg/dl	<200 mg/dl
Triglycerides	244 mg /dl	<200 mg/dl
HDL Cholesterol	45 mg/dl	35-65 mg/dl
LDL Cholesterol	98 mg/dl	<150 mg/dl
PT	12 Seconds	12 -15 Seconds
INR	1	0.9-1.1
aPTT	29 Seconds	29-43 Seconds
ANA	Negative	Negative
Anti-dsDNA	Negative	Negative
ACR	3726mg/g	Normal <30 mg/g

ALT: Alanine Transaminase; ALP: Alkaline Phosphatase ; ESR: Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate; HCV: Hepatitis C Virus; HbsAg: Hepatitis B Surface Antigen ; MCV : Mean Corpuscular Volume ; HIV : Human Immunodeficiency Virus ; BUN : Blood Urea Nitrogen ; CRP: C-Reactive Protein ; ACR: Albumin-to-Creatinine Ratio; ANA; Anti Nuclear Antibody, Anti-dsDNA; anti-double stranded DNA

TABLE 2: Routine urine exam

Urine R.E	Value	Reference Range
Colour	Yellow	Yellow
Appearance	Clear	Clear
Glucose	Nil	Negative
pH	8.0	4.5-8.0
Protein	Positive(+)	Negative
PUS/WBC	5-10	0-5/HPF
RBC	Numerous	0-5/HPF
Epithelial Cells	Positive(+)	0-10/HPF
Hyaline Cast	Negative (-)	0-4/HPF
Granular Cast	Negative (-)	0/HPF
Amorphous Urates	Nil	Nil

RBC : Red Blood Cells ; WBC : White Blood Cells ; HPF: High-powered field ; R.E : routine examination

TABLE 3: 24 hours urinary protein

Protein- 24 Hours Urine	Value	Reference Range
Volume	1700 ml	1500-2000 ml
24 Hours Urinary Protein	11752 mg/ 24 hours	< 150 mg/ 24 hours

Figure 1 : H&E stain at 10x magnification show **endocapillary proliferative pattern of glomerulonephritis** (white arrow)

Figure 2 : H&E stain at 40x magnification show **endocapillary proliferative pattern of glomerulonephritis** (white arrow)

DISCUSSION:

Full-house nephropathy is typically linked to lupus nephritis, which is identified through a combination of clinical signs and serological markers of Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE), as well as specific findings on a renal biopsy [7]. However, in the discussed patient's situation, there were no clinical indications of lupus. Additionally, tests for antinuclear antibodies (ANA), anti-double stranded DNA (anti-dsDNA), and complement levels (C3, C4) all returned results within normal ranges. This effectively excluded SLE as a diagnosis for the patient [8].

Instances of full-house nephropathy occurring outside of lupus contexts have been documented in a variety of glomerular diseases. These include membranous nephropathy (MN), IgA nephropathy, membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis (MPGN), post-infectious glomerulonephritis (PIGN), C1Q nephropathy, and some cases of unclassified mesangial glomerulonephritis. However, it is important to note that such occurrences are relatively rare [4]. The discovery of IgA deposits in this particular patient suggests a potential overlap with IgA nephropathy, a condition characterized by the deposition of mesangial IgA. In some instances of IgA nephropathy, there is also a concurrent presence of IgG, IgM, and various complement components [10]. Furthermore, the patient's biopsy revealed mild tubular and interstitial changes, which is unusual given

the severe nephrotic-range proteinuria presented. Commonly, such significant proteinuria is associated with more extensive tubulointerstitial damage [11]. The minimal tubulointerstitial damage observed in this case emphasizes its exceptional nature.

The detection of eosinophils in the renal interstitium points towards a potential case of drug-induced interstitial nephritis [6]. While the patient's history did not specifically mention any medication, this finding, coupled with the overall renal pathology, indicates the need for further exploration into possible nephrotoxic substances. Eosinophilic infiltrates are rarely mentioned in association with full-house nephropathy, which adds a layer of uniqueness to this case.

Considering the distinctive array of findings, this case presents an unusual instance of full-house nephropathy not linked to lupus, characterized by severe proteinuria and comparably mild renal damage. This underscores the complexity and variability of renal pathologies, highlighting the importance of comprehensive diagnostic evaluations in identifying rare and atypical presentations of renal diseases.

CONCLUSION:

This case brings attention to the uncommon occurrence of full-house nephropathy without systemic lupus erythematosus. The presence of severe proteinuria, mild histopathological changes, and the absence of lupus serology in this case make it a

distinctive presentation of non-lupus full-house nephropathy. Further research into the underlying causes of full-house nephropathy without lupus is necessary, as this condition is not well understood.

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